

Ethical and Responsible Journalism Resulting in Impactful Engagement with Refugee/Migrant Populations during the COVID-19 Pandemic

In advocating for ethical and responsible journalism when engaging with refugee/migrant populations during this pandemic, here are some ethical principles to reflect:

Solidarity

- Both parties have a common interest and objective and hence, should be united in supporting measures to achieve this goal. However, contributing to achieving this common goal will also depend on our individual situations.
- Acting in the common interest may mean that parties may have to make some sacrifices in order to achieve the goal. For example, articles that are less sensational may not be circulated as widely or as quickly.
- It is important to remember that every person has a role to play.
- While journalists may be working under pressure (and this is understandably so as these are challenging times), it is good to keep in mind certain ethical principles. It may be useful to consider the following questions in relation to your sphere of influence and action:
 - What is my role in this specific situation?
 - How can I be a part of the solution?
- For journalists, the answer to these questions should reflect the unique position and skills you have, which you can contribute to this effort.

Embracing the spirit of solidarity, the next ethical principle to keep in mind would be:

Respecting persons and treating them with dignity

- It is important to be mindful that each and every person deserves to be treated with dignity.
- Unfortunately, certain groups of people are typically not treated with dignity and have little or no influence to challenge their situations.
- In the best of circumstances, refugees are discriminated against socially, economically marginalised and lack any long-term security.
- This is significantly compounded by the COVID-19 situation where they will be faced with even more stigmatisation and discrimination.
- Treating them with dignity requires everyone to recognise and mitigate these risks.
- As a society, we owe it to them in the spirit of solidarity so that **they** can play their part without fear of social or governmental reprisals.

If language and communication skills are your armoury, use them to the best effect. Endeavour to foster the spirit of solidarity, be mindful of harming it.

The WHO and a number of UN agencies have developed helpful and practical tools that can be used to promote responsible journalism¹. Referring to them is a good step in the right direction.

¹ World Health Organisation, 2020. A guide to preventing and addressing social stigma. Available from: <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/covid19-stigma-guide.pdf>